

ASSESSMENT OF THE STATE OF THE GENITAL TRACT MICROBIOCENOSIS IN PREGNANT WOMEN WITH PREMATURE RUPTURE OF THE MEMBRANES USING THE FEMOFLOR TEST

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Annation. *Premature discharge of amniotic fluid (amniotic fluid), being one of the most frequent complications of pregnancy and childbirth, is still the main cause of the high frequency of obstetric injuries, surgical delivery and neonatal complications. The microflora of the urogenital tract of women is a collection of microorganisms that causes resistance to colonization, pH stability of the vaginal mucosa, participates in the maintenance of local immunity and, as a result, ensures the body's general resistance to infections . The normal microflora of the vagina of healthy women of reproductive age includes gram-positive and gram-negative aerobic, facultative aerobic and obligate anaerobic microorganisms, 95-98% of all microorganisms are lactobacilli.*

Key words: *pregnant women with premature rupture of membranes, genital tract biocenosis, polymerase chain reaction, preterm birth, vaginal microbiocenosis.*

The purpose of the study is to determine the qualitative and quantitative composition of microorganisms that make up the microbiocenosis of the genital tract in pregnant women with premature discharge using PCR.

Research materials and methods. Vaginal swabs of 28 pregnant women who came to the perinatal center with discharge before the period of 26-34 weeks and 24-36 years of age were studied. The control group consisted of 11 pregnant

women aged 24-36 with a physiologically developing pregnancy of 20-25 weeks. We used PZR (Femoflor-16) and the DT-96 detection amplification reagent kit manufactured by OOO "NPO DNK-Technology" (Russia) to study the biocenosis of the urogenital tract in women. Samples with sufficient number of cells and sufficient total bacterial mass from the vagina and partial cervix were used to obtain appropriate results. Samples were considered in which the DNA content of human cells was greater than 104 genome-equivalents (GE) in the sample and the total bacterial mass value was 106 to 109 GE/sample.

Research results. Comparison of indicators of biocenosis in the compared groups showed that the proportion of normocenosis in women with premature amniotic fluid was 2.5 times lower than in the control group ($p=0.0019$). Dysbiosis was detected in 18 out of 28 cases (64.3%), and in the control group in 1 out of 11 women (9.1%; $p=0.0019$). Average anaerobic, pronounced aerobic and mixed dysbiosis was found only in the main group of women. Anaerobic bacteria were detected faster than aerobes, which corresponds to the results obtained earlier. Of the main group, 9 (32.1%) pregnant women, including 7 (25.0%) had anaerobic dysbiosis, 2 (7.1%) had aerobic dysbiosis. In severe dysbiosis, *Lactobacillus spp.* amount is from 0 to 18% of the total bacterial mass. *Streptococcus spp.* observed in high titers. In one of the patients, along with streptococci, we detected fungi of the genus *Candida* in the diagnostic titer. In both cases *Lactobacillus spp.* not defined. Moderate aerobic-anaerobic (mixed) dysbiosis was also detected in 2 patients. In 1 patient with mixed dysbiosis, the following were detected: *Streptococcus spp./Gardnerella vaginalis/Prevolla bivia/Porphyrromonas spp.*, in another case *Megasphaera spp./Veillonella spp./Dialister spp./Ureaplasma (urealyticum+parvum)*.

Summary. Thus, as a result of the study, the effectiveness of using a new modern PCR method for the diagnosis of bacterial vaginosis was shown. The method allows to determine the number of lactobacilli and bacteria associated with bacterial vaginosis, anaerobic and aerobic flora, including difficult-to-cultivate flora, and to

assess their ratio and the state of the biocenosis of the female genital tract in a short period of time. For the first time, using the Femoflor test, the microbial landscape of the genital tract of women with premature ejaculation was compared with the microbiocenosis of the genital tract of women with physiological pregnancy. In 64.3% of cases *Lactobacillus spp.* a decrease in the percentage, bacterial imbalance was detected in pregnant women with premature amniocentesis.